

The convenient microwave-assisted synthesis, characterization and structural study of substituted bis-[1,2,4]-dithiazolidines

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Abstract : A convenient synthesis of substituted bis-[1,2,4]-dithiazolidines has been developed by using the environment-friendly technique of microwave irradiation. The microwave-assisted synthesis of several members of the titled class has been achieved by the interaction of 1-{4-[4-(3-aryl thiocarbamido)-3-nitro/carboxy-benzyl]-2-nitro/carboxy-phenyl}-3-aryl thiocarbamides with *N*-phenyl-*S*-chloro isothiocarbamoyl chloride under solvent-free condition, followed by basification with dilute ammonium hydroxide solution. Initially, 1-{4-[4-(3-aryl thiocarbamido)-3-nitro/carboxy-benzyl]-2-nitro/carboxy-phenyl}-3-aryl thiocarbamides were prepared by irradiating the mixtures of different aryl isothiocyanates with 4,4'-methylene-bis-(2-nitro-aniline)/(anthranilic acid) under microwave for specified time. The constitutions of synthesized compounds have been delineated on the basis of chemical transformation, elemental analysis, equivalent weight determination, IR and ¹H NMR spectral studies.

Keywords : Microwave-assisted synthesis, structural study, bis-[1,2,4]-dithiazolidines.

Introduction

The synthesis and antimicrobial evaluation of various pharmacologically important [1,2,4]-dithiazolidines have been reported earlier¹. The literature has been enriched with progressive findings about the synthesis of [1,2,4]-dithiazolidines by using the reagent *N*-phenyl-*S*-chloro isothiocarbamoyl chloride and by oxidative cyclization using bromine and iodine². [1,2,4]-Dithiazolidines have been found to have potent anti-inflammatory and antitumor properties as they downregulate the NF-κB transcription factor³. Various substituted [1,2,4]-dithiazolidines are known for their medicinal activities particularly as anti-bacterial and antifungal agents⁴. In view of the utility of *N*-phenyl-*S*-chloro isothiocarbamoyl chloride in the synthesis of nitrogen- and sulphur-containing heterocyclic compounds and as a part of our research towards the development of efficient and environmentally benign methodologies using eco-friendly conditions⁵, we report herein the microwave-assisted synthesis of bis-[1,2,4]-dithiazolidine derivatives.

Results and discussion

The compounds 4,4'-methylene-bis-(2-nitroaniline) (**1**) and 4,4'-methylene-bis-(anthranilic acid) (**4**) were transformed into 1-{4-[4-(3-aryl thiocarbamido)-3-nitrobenzyl]-2-nitrophenyl}-3-aryl thiocarbamides (**2a-g**) and 1-{4-[4-(3-aryl thiocarbamido)-3-carboxybenzyl]-2-carboxyphenyl}-3-aryl thiocarbamides (**5a-g**) by condensing that with different aryl isothiocyanates (0.02 mol) under microwave (800 W) for 45 and 60 s, respectively (Scheme 1).

The compounds (**2a-g**) and (**5a-g**) were then reacted with *N*-phenyl-*S*-chloro isothiocarbamoyl chloride (0.02 mol) under MWI in solvent-free condition for the said time periods. Cooling the reaction mixtures afforded sticky masses, which on washing with petroleum ether gave granular solids. These were acidic to litmus and, on titrimetric analysis, these were identified as 4-{4-[4-(5-arylimino-3-phenylimino-[1,2,4]-dithiazolidin-4-yl)-3-nitrobenzyl]-2-nitrophenyl}-5-arylimino-3-phenylimino-[1,2,4]-dithiazolidine dihydrochlorides and 4-{4-[4-(5-

where, **1, 2a-c** : R = H, 4-CH₃, 4-Cl and R' = NO₂
4, 5a-c : R = H, 4-CH₃, 4-Cl and R' = COOH

Scheme 1

arylimino-3-phenylimino-[1,2,4]-dithiazolidin-4-yl)-3-carboxybenzyl]-2-carboxyphenyl}-5-arylimino-3-phenylimino-[1,2,4]-dithiazolidine dihydrochlorides. These on basification with dilute ammonium hydroxide solution afforded free bases (**3a-g**) and (**6a-g**) (Scheme 2).

where, **2, 3a-c** : R = H, 4-CH₃, 4-Cl and R' = NO₂
5, 6a-c : R = H, 4-CH₃, 4-Cl and R' = COOH

Scheme 2

Experimental

The microwave-assisted reactions were carried out using a microwave oven (Godrej, GMG-20E-08-SLGX).

Melting points were recorded using a digital melting point apparatus (Veego, VMP-D) and are uncorrected. Chemicals used were of AR grade. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded with TMS as internal standard using CDCl₃ and DMSO-*d*₆ as solvents. IR spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer in the range 4000–400 cm⁻¹ in nujol mull and as KBr pellets. Purity of the compounds was checked by TLC on silica gel-G plates.

Synthesis of 1-{2-nitro-4-[3-nitro-4-(3-phenyl thiocarbamido)-benzyl]-phenyl}-3-phenyl thiocarbamide (**2a**) :

A mixture of 4,4'-methylene-bis(2-nitroaniline) (0.01 mol) and phenyl isothiocyanate (0.02 mol) was irradiated under microwave for 45 s. After irradiation, the reaction mixture was cooled, a solid mass was obtained. It was crystallized from ethanol to yield 1-{2-nitro-4-[3-nitro-4-(3-phenyl thiocarbamido)-benzyl]-phenyl}-3-phenyl thiocarbamide, **2a** (85%), m.p. 57–58 °C (Found : N, 14.97; S, 11.32. Calcd. for C₂₇H₂₂N₆O₄S₂ : N, 15.05; S, 11.46%); ν_{max} 3406, 3389 (NH), 1520 (N=O), 1316 (C-N), 1232 cm⁻¹ (C=S); δ (CDCl₃ + DMSO-*d*₆) : 6.66–7.16 (16H, m, Ar-H), 4.43 (4H, s, NH), 2.71 (2H, s, CH₂)⁶.

Compounds **2b** and **2c** were prepared in a similar manner.

2b (82%), m.p. 62 °C (Found : N, 14.34; S, 10.88. Calcd. for C₂₉H₂₆N₆O₄S₂ : N, 14.33; S, 10.92%); **2c** (80%), m.p. 78 °C (Found : N, 13.31; S, 10.07. Calcd. for C₂₇H₂₀N₆O₄S₂Cl₂ : N, 13.39; S, 10.20%).

Synthesis of 4-{4-[4-(3,5-bis-phenylimino-[1,2,4]-dithiazolidin-4-yl)-3-nitro-benzyl]-2-nitro-phenyl}-3,5-bis-phenylimino-[1,2,4]-dithiazolidine (**3a**) :

The compound 1-{2-nitro-4-[3-nitro-4-(3-phenyl thiocarbamido)-benzyl]-phenyl}-3-phenyl thiocarbamide (**2a**) (0.01 mol) was mixed well with *N*-phenyl-*S*-chloro isothiocarbonyl chloride (0.02 mol) and subjected to MWI under solvent-free condition. The reaction was completed within 60 s. After cooling the reaction mixture, a sticky mass was obtained. It was repeatedly washed with petroleum ether (60–80 °C), followed by the addition of ethanol. It was acidic to litmus and on determination of equivalent weight found be 4-{4-[4-(3,5-bis-phenylimino-[1,2,4]-dithiazolidin-4-yl)-3-nitrobenzyl]-2-nitrophenyl}-3,5-bis-phenylimino-[1,2,4]-dithiazolidine dihydro-

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chloride, m.p. 78–79 °C. On basification with dilute ammonium hydroxide solution, it provided a free base which was crystallized from ethanol and identified as 4-{4-[4-(3,5-bis-phenylimino-[1,2,4]-dithiazolidin-4-yl)-3-nitrobenzyl]-2-nitrophenyl}-3,5-bis-phenylimino-[1,2,4]-dithiazolidine, **3a** (80%), m.p. 171 °C (Found : C, 59.02; H, 3.30; N, 13.62; S, 15.44. Calcd. for $C_{41}H_{28}N_8O_4S_4$: C, 59.70; H, 3.39; N, 13.59; S, 15.53%); ν_{\max} 1629 (C=N), 1512 (N=O), 1341 (C-N), 742 (C-S), 428 cm^{-1} (S-S); δ ($CDCl_3$ +DMSO- d_6) : 6.98–8.02 (26H, m, Ar-H), 2.65 (2H, s, CH_2).

Compounds **3b** and **3c** were similarly prepared.

3b (85%), m.p. 158 °C (Found : C, 60.33; H, 3.60; N, 13.08; S, 14.87. Calcd. for $C_{43}H_{32}N_8O_4S_4$: C, 60.56; H, 3.75; N, 13.14; S, 15.02%); ν_{\max} 1342 (C=N), 1516 (N=O), 1322 (C-N), 728 (C-S), 420 cm^{-1} (S-S); δ ($CDCl_3$ + DMSO- d_6) : 6.78–7.98 (24H, m, Ar-H), 2.59 (2H, s, CH_2), 2.29 (6H, s, Ar- CH_3); **3c** (82%), m.p. 110 °C (Found : C, 54.88; H, 2.89; N, 12.51; S, 14.22. Calcd. for $C_{41}H_{26}N_8O_4S_4Cl_2$: C, 55.09; H, 2.91; N, 12.54; S, 14.33%).

Synthesis of 1-{2-carboxy-4-[3-carboxy-4-(3-phenyl thiocarbamido)-benzyl]-phenyl}-3-phenyl thiocarbamide (5a) :

A mixture of 4,4'-methylene-bis-(anthranilic acid) (**4**) (0.01 mol) and phenyl isothiocyanate (0.02 mol) was subjected to MWI for 60 s. After completion of the reaction, the reaction mixture was cooled when a solid mass was obtained. It was crystallized from ethanol to yield 1-{2-carboxy-4-[3-carboxy-4-(3-phenylthiocarbamido)-benzyl]phenyl}-3-phenyl thiocarbamide, **5a** (82%), m.p. 210 °C (Found : N, 9.85; S, 11.44. Calcd. for $C_{29}H_{24}N_4O_4S_2$: N, 10.07; S, 11.51%); ν_{\max} 3481, 3446 (NH), 3212 (OH), 1710 (C=O), 1318 (C-N), 1231 cm^{-1} (C=S); δ ($CDCl_3$ + DMSO- d_6) : 8.02 (2H, s, OH), 6.75–7.92 (16H, m, Ar-H), 4.38 (4H, s, NH), 2.51 (2H, s, CH_2)^{16,17}.

This reaction was extended to synthesize other compounds **5b** and **5c**.

5b (85%), m.p. 204 °C (Found : N, 9.39; S, 10.89. Calcd. for $C_{31}H_{28}N_4O_4S_2$: N, 9.58; S, 10.95); **5c** (80%), m.p. 195–196 °C (Found : N, 8.81; S, 10.22. Calcd. for $C_{29}H_{22}N_4O_4S_2Cl_2$: N, 8.96; S, 10.24%).

Synthesis of 4-{4-[4-(3,5-bis-phenylimino-[1,2,4]-dithiazolidin-4-yl)-3-carboxy-benzyl]-2-carboxy-phenyl}-3,5-bis-phenylimino-[1,2,4]-dithiazolidine (6a) :

The compound 1-{2-carboxy-4-[3-carboxy-4-(3-phenyl thiocarbamido)-benzyl]-phenyl}-3-phenyl thiocarbamide (**5a**) (0.01 mol) was mixed well with *N*-phenyl-*S*-chloro isothiocarbamoyl chloride (0.02 mol) and subjected to MWI solvent-free condition. The reaction was completed within 85 s. After cooling the reaction mixture, a sticky mass was obtained. It was repeatedly washed with petroleum ether (60–80 °C), followed by the addition of ethanol. It was acidic to litmus and on determination of equivalent weight found be 4-{4-[4-(3,5-bis-phenylimino-[1,2,4]-dithiazolidin-4-yl)-3-carboxybenzyl]-2-carboxyphenyl}-3,5-bis-phenylimino-[1,2,4]-dithiazolidine dihydrochloride, m.p. 198 °C. It, on basification with dilute ammonium hydroxide solution, afforded a free base. It was crystallized from ethanol and identified as 4-{4-[4-(3,5-bis-phenylimino-[1,2,4]-dithiazolidin-4-yl)-3-carboxybenzyl]-2-carboxyphenyl}-3,5-bis-phenylimino-[1,2,4]-dithiazolidine, **6a** (85%), m.p. 182 °C (Found : C, 61.91; H, 3.57; N, 10.22; S, 15.55. Calcd. for $C_{43}H_{30}N_6O_4S_4$: C, 62.77; H, 3.64; N, 10.21; S, 15.57%); ν_{\max} 3228 (OH), 1706 (C=O), 1623 (C=N), 1333 (C-N), 752 (C-S), 422 cm^{-1} (S-S); δ ($CDCl_3$ + DMSO- d_6) : 8.16 (2H, s, OH), 6.78–7.71 (26H, m, Ar-H), 2.61 (2H, s, CH_2).

This reaction was extended to synthesize other compounds **6b** and **6c**.

6b (80%), m.p. 202 °C (Found : C, 62.67; H, 3.90; N, 9.78; S, 14.87. Calcd. for $C_{45}H_{34}N_6O_4S_4$: C, 63.52; H, 4.00; N, 9.88; S, 15.05%); ν_{\max} 3193 (OH), 1708 (C=O), 1621 (C=N), 1327 (C-N), 741 (C-S), 415 cm^{-1} (S-S); δ ($CDCl_3$ + DMSO- d_6) : 8.23 (2H, s, OH), 6.92–7.88 (24H, m, Ar-H), 2.55 (2H, s, CH_2), 2.35 (6H, s, Ar- CH_3); **6c** (80%), m.p. 187 °C (Found : C, 57.66; H, 3.11; N, 9.40; S, 14.26. Calcd. for $C_{43}H_{28}N_6O_4S_4Cl_2$: C, 57.91; H, 3.14; N, 9.42; S, 14.36%).

Conclusion

In the present work, the synthesis of 4-{4-[4-(5-arylimino-3-phenylimino-[1,2,4]-dithiazolidin-4-yl)-3-nitrobenzyl]-2-nitrophenyl}-5-arylimino-3-phenylimino-[1,2,4]-dithiazolidines (**3a-c**) and 4-{4-[4-(5-arylimino-3-phenylimino-[1,2,4]-dithiazolidin-4-yl)-3-carboxybenzyl]-

2-carboxyphenyl}-5-arylimino-3-phenylimino-[1,2,4]-dithiazolidines (**6a-c**) has been reported. The method applied for the synthesis is quite simple, efficient and in compliance with the green chemistry protocols, requires extremely mild reaction conditions and completed within a short period of time with high yield.

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